

Revolutionizing customer care support: An exploration of artificial intelligence applications and benefits

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Abstract:

This paper is aimed on providing a comprehensive analysis on usage of Artificial intelligence on increasing effective customer support and feedback. Artificial intelligence is capable of real time, data collection, learning and outputting responses that require minimum to none human interaction. Most conventional businesses are still using human involvement in customer support which poses them with major issues such as availability, effective problem solving and cost. Artificial intelligence is a cheap solution that acts as a competent agent in this matter.

The purpose of this paper is to discuss about the involvement of artificial intelligence in human expertise-based matter and its effectiveness whilst providing real life examples on effective usage of Artificial intelligence in customer care, the problems it poses in contrast to the traditional system and ways of resolving these issues in order to gain its maximum effectiveness.

Methodology: Theoretical material derived from current literature from many sources such as reputable journals, news stories, and other feasible domains are used in this study.

Conclusion/findings: The research proves that given the technology limitations in the current century, constant review and monitoring of AI based chatbots, applications are required in order to use their maximum potentials.

Introduction

Artificial intelligence (AI) is one of contemporary technology's most important and constantly expanding topics. AI has become a commonplace aspect of our daily lives, and its potential applications are numerous and diverse. AI has the potential to change numerous businesses and facets of our life, from driverless vehicles to medical diagnostics, virtual assistants to fraud detection. As a result, there is an increasing demand for study on AI's capabilities, limits, and ethical implications.

Artificial intelligence has been heavy on promises and short on delivery since its inception. Pioneers such as Marvin Minsky, John McCarthy, and Herb Simon honestly felt that AI might be solved before the end of the twentieth century in the 1950s and 1960s. (Marcus, G. and Davis, E., 2019) However AI has come a long way and currently in year 2023 AI has reached almost the pinnacle of machine learning and natural language usage. Many organizations, companies have already implemented the use of AI in various fields. We can discover a plethora of natural language contact with intelligent agents on the internet, ranging from airline reservation systems to goods catalogs, implying that humans have little to no issue translating their language abilities to such applications. Because so much of this communication takes place through digital technology rather than in person, computer-mediated communication (or "CMC") has emerged as a popular topic of study for investigating this mimic of real human language. (Hill J, Farreras, I.G., 2015) The use of chatbots have been around for quite sometime as it was used on many websites as a very useful feature. Some of the reasons why chatbots have grown so popular in business organizations include lower customer service expenses and the capacity to manage several customers at once. (Ranoliya, B.R., Raghuwanshi, N., 2017) They have become more human like and plays a role as an assistant in assisting anything no matter the time. An Harvard Business Review study showed that 39% of worldwide organizations use AI Technology to enhance the brand experience. (Wilson, H. J, 2017)

This research paper attempts to offer an overview of the present status of artificial intelligence (AI), major ideas and techniques, applications in the industries, ethical issues surrounding its usage and finally the conclusion and the future that lies ahead for AI technology.

2. Literature review

2.1 Maximizing customer care service

Any business or organization depends on their customer's loyalty and their trust on the brand. There are many causes that depend on gaining this trust however the care that a company provides for their customers is a crucial part in the industry. Customer service is the assistance you provide to your consumers both before and after they purchase and utilize your products or services, allowing them to have a simple and happy experience with you.

Both academic studies and top service firms have identified the idea of 'quality of service' as a competitive advantage in obtaining market leadership. But, in an increasingly competitive market, it has become increasingly crucial for firms to develop strategies to not just achieve the top, but also to preserve that leadership. Service firms are looking for strategies to establish and sustain ongoing relationships with their consumers in order to safeguard their long-term interests. (Kandampully J, 2010)

Customer service has several elements, the significance of which varies depending on the sector. These dimensions might include, among other things, pre-sales service, delivery reliability and speed, product technical assistance (after-sales service), and reaction to client inquiries. A favorable relationship has been shown between customer service and corporate performance. (Vickery, Jayaram, Droge & Calantone, 2003).

For a while now customer service was solely based on human interaction, telephone conversation and with the invention of the internet websites and email were seen in the process as well. However new technologies have replaced these conventional methods. Digitalization also represents the shift from a product-centric to a service-centric company paradigm. The most significant improvements in the field of interaction have been created by new information technology, which has resulted in a move from mass marketing to individual marketing, which directs each customer's demands individually. (Muther, 2002, p. 91; Matzner & Büttgen, 2018, p. 7).

2.2 AI implementation as chatbots

The phrase "chatbot" is a combination of the verb "chatting" with the noun "robot" (Rese, A et al,2020). A chatbot is a conversational software system that simulates human-like communication abilities in order to connect with a user via chat. (Nuruzzaman, M. et al, 2018)

In accordance to this study stream's consensus, customers, employees, and businesses will soon realize a future in which "people and robots act synergistically" (Haesevoets et al. 2021, p. 2). AI can maximize the satisfaction while saving a considerable amount of time. Chatbots can recognize essential terms in a customer's request and, as a result, provide the best feasible solutions to consumer problems through logical responses. Furthermore, after each usage, the database from which the information is gathered is updated and expanded, allowing future customers' issues to be solved even faster and in greater depth (Kaplan et al 2019) Similarly, because users or consumers are frequently obliged to search and explore a website for an extended period of time, chatbots provide a quick, simple, and efficient option to retrieving such information as quickly as possible. Problem-solving appears to be an important component in judging service effectiveness and, as such, to play a mediating role in consumer choice for chatbots or human customer support.

Companies are moving their attention away from sales objectives and toward emotional bonds with their consumers. Satisfying the target audience and recognizing the particular issues that clients face is seen as a critical concern. The amount of pleasure coming from the relationship and the client's emotional commitment to this relationship determine the quality of the relationship between the firm and the client. (Pansari & Kumar, 2017, pp. 295–298) since they expect valuable information, feel respected, and be encouraged in their purchasing process by engaging in a nice conversation. AI however face issues in this matter as the language models have not peaked as they are expected to be. Nevertheless, it is their lack of humanity, rather than their technological traits, that may raise worries about their interaction capacities. Chatbots, for example, may fail to match users' expectations regarding the chatbot's linguistic abilities, which may result in negative feelings such as dissatisfaction at not being adequately understood. Additionally, the lack of human communication styles, such as gesture and voice, might exacerbate interaction issues. (Rapp et al 2021). ChatGpt which became a recent sensation is a natural language processing tool powered by AI technology that allows you to have human-like discussions, this piece of software has taken another step forward and converted into plugins that can be manipulated with customer care help as well. In relation to the older versions of chatbots that are trained on specific data sets, Chatgpt can identify and respond in a custom manner. In the case of premium companies, for example, consumer demands are particularly precise, since clients want to be handled in a personalized and distinctive manner. As a result, rather of addressing a broad audience, products and services tailored to the requirements and preferences of the individual client are supplied (Chung et al). Customers of banks appear to have specific expectations regarding the service they receive. As a response, Bank of America has introduced Erica, its very own chatbot that offers financial recommendations based on the customer's spending patterns. (Cui et al 2017)

New technologies are not the only driving forces behind the changing customer value creation. The role of regulation is remarkable especially in the financial sector, where it has traditionally protected incumbent service providers from competition. For example, however, the European Union's new Payment Services Directive (PSD2) opens competition for new entrants to use information on consumer payment accounts if they have an appropriate license and the customer's consent. The changing influence of regulation – with new entrants that include not only FinTech start-ups but also technology giants such as Google, Amazon, and Alibaba – can dramatically change the competition landscape, generate new operation modes, and affect customer expectations of financial services.

Conclusion

This paper has explored the transformative role of artificial intelligence (AI) in revolutionizing customer care support. By examining the potential benefits, such as cost-effectiveness, 24/7 availability, and improved problem-solving capabilities, AI technologies like chatbots have proven to enhance customer service experiences. However, the study also highlighted the challenges AI faces, particularly the need for continuous monitoring and improvement to reach its full potential. While AI-based systems can streamline customer care, their lack of human-like emotional intelligence and context-awareness remain limitations.

To maximize the effectiveness of AI in customer service, organizations must strike a balance between human and AI-driven solutions. Regular updates, data improvements, and the integration of more sophisticated AI models like ChatGPT are crucial to refining customer interactions. As AI technology evolves, the future of customer care is likely to see a more seamless blend of human and machine efforts, creating more efficient, personalized, and responsive services that meet the increasing demands of the digital age.

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